

The Names of Herdsmen in the Middle English Language: Historical Development of the Lexical-Thematic Group

Galvijų augintojų pavadinimai
vidurinėje anglų kalboje:
leksinės-teminės grupės
istorinis vystymasis

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The article is devoted to the general purpose of the study of the etymological composition, functional differentiation and chronological stratification of the thematic group of Middle English names of farm-workers (herdsmen). Middle English occupational terms are distributed into two classes – common names (in their nominating function) and proper names, especially family names (in the function of identification of the person as the component additional to the personal name in the personal nomination formula). Within each etymological group of vocabulary we distribute the lexical material according to the functional principle and distinguish three groups of occupational terms: those functioning as common nouns as well as the proper names; those functioning exclusively as the proper names in the personal nomination formulas; those functioning exclusively as common names. It was found out that the thematic subgroup of Middle English names of herdsmen is represented by 157 words comprising 6.5 % of the total number of Middle English occupational terms; 90 % of them are English words (24 % of them are loan-blends), 10 % are loan-words. Functional differentiation of the vocabulary is different in English and borrowed occupational terms. Chronological stratification of the lexical-thematic subgroup indicates their predominance in the thirteenth century (42 %), as well as in the XIVth century (54 %). Data obtained in the study under review are valuable as the constituent part of the comprehensive study of the etymology and usage of the Middle English vocabulary.

KEYWORDS: Middle English, occupational terms, the names of herdsmen, etymology, functional differentiation, chronological stratification

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Abstract

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Introduction

The relevance of the topic of our article is predetermined by the following factors: first, it is the need for obtaining a new knowledge on the history of the lexical system in the form of the description of its evolution or historical development that has been interpreted as the gradual complication and, therefore, improving, on the basis of the general concept of linguistic change; second, it is the need to study the influence of other languages and the process of borrowing, lexical borrowings in particular, which is the implementation of social and socio-cultural influences, as well as the historical life of the people and progress of human society as a whole (it holds significance among the factors of language development, since the interaction of language with other languages determine the specifics of the history of particular language as a result of their joint history).

Theoretical Background/ Literature Review

In the late Middle Ages England remained a predominantly agricultural country (King, 1979, p.91). Despite the growth of cities and fast development of crafts and trade, agriculture remained the main occupation of most of the population (Myers, 1978, p.54). Stratification of the peasantry, the emergence of capitalist relations of production that characterized the development of the Medieval English village, gradually led to the increase in the share of hired labour in agricultural production (Kosminskiy, 1947, p.365). It proves the fact of deep specialization, and gives reason to consider Middle English names of people employed in agriculture as the names of occupation (Solonovich, 1986).

In the dissertation thesis of T. Solonovich there were identified 150 words within the thematic subgroup of the names of farm-workers, comprising 8.5 % of the total number 1771 of the occupational names in the English language of the XI–XV centuries (Solonovich, 1986, p.176). The scholar noted the growth of this lexical-thematic subgroup as compared to Anglo-Saxon period, which, according to her calculations, had 38 words denoting farm-workers (Solonovich, 1986, p.149). The role of borrowings as a means of nomination of persons in the lexical-thematic subgroup of Middle English farm-workers is extremely slight: it was detected only 12 of borrowed lexical units, which comprise 8 % of their total number (two of them are of Latin origin, eight of them are of French origin, two of them have double, Latin and French, origin). In addition, there were identified eight loan-blends, as well as five loan-words of French origin that entered the English language along with their motivational basis (Solonovich, 1986, p.150).

In modern theory of language it is highly evaluated a comprehensive study of the vocabulary, i. e., an integrative description of the influence of external factors upon the functioning and development of the lexical structure of the language, in diachronic terms. As far as the research of T. Solonovich has an onomasiological and derivational specification, and the study of the functional distribution of the vocabulary was not targeted, the delineation of the vocabulary into the levels of common and proper names wasn't aimed as it wasn't feasible at all. In our article we take a holistic approach to the study of language objects – the general synchronous-diachronic approach to the study of linguistic phenomena throughout the stages of the research with the application of several techniques of theoretical and empirical research methods: we classify the vocabulary according to the etymology determining the language – the source of borrowing, which is not always the same as the language – the origin of the word, semantics, functional differentiation (habitualness of usage) and chronology.

Summarizing the scientific achievements of many scholars, we draw the conclusion as to the topicality of study of the correlations of specific and borrowed phenomena, basing on a large empirical material and long chronological layer, being observed in several varieties of functioning of the vocabulary in line with the systemic-structural paradigm, with the aim to establish the role and place of borrowings in the process of assimilation as an external factor

of language evolution with the general goal to reconstruct the Middle English vocabulary by means of identification of language changes – functional and system formal and semantic, – which are the result of the joint action of external and internal factors of language history.

We have studied 238 names of farm-workers in the Middle English language (150 of them have English origin, 65 are the loan-blends, 23 are the loan-words) and we have already described the etymology, lexical-semantic distribution and functional differentiation of 66 names of farmers (Dobrovolska, 2016). Beyond these names, according to our calculations, there are two more subgroups: the names of gardeners (15 words) and the names of herdsmen (157 words). The latter had been put into the focus of our special attention in this paper and had become the **object** of our study.

The subject of the study is the following – the etymology, lexical-thematic distribution, functional differentiation and chronological stratification of the Middle English names of farm-workers, esp. those in charge of domestic animals.

The **problem** to be solved in this paper is as follows: the reconstruction of the evolution of the lexical-thematic subgroup of the Middle English names of farm-workers, who were taking care of domestic animals, by means of distinguishing of its etymological composition, functional differentiation, lexical-thematic distribution and chronological stratification.

The article proves **the hypothesis of the study**, which is based on the assumption the fact that the Middle English occupational terms were of mixed origin; lexical borrowing having been the major (but not the leading) means of its replenishment, which was mainly due to the native English) sources of word formation; and the reconstruction of the evolution of the thematic group of herdsmen through the prism of correlation of specific and borrowed, as well as their functional differentiation and chronological stratification is a confirmation of the gradual complication and improvement of the English language as the directions of its evolution.

Our research is conducted in line with the functional-systemic approach to the language study: when describing historical transformations of the vocabulary of the English language, we use the system analysis in combination with the functional approach, which takes into account the heterogeneity of language in its multifunctioning.

Theoretical basis of the functional method is the consideration of language as a dynamic system, that is being in constant motion and development. The main tenet of the functional linguistics is the thesis that language is the instrument, the means and the mechanism for the implementation of certain human intentions – both in the field of cognition and in the acts of communication. Central concern of functionalism is the study of the function of the object as well as its purpose and features from the point of view of the missions, being adapted to their implementation (Levitskij, 2006, p.122).

The influence of other languages and the process of linguistic borrowing, especially the lexical borrowing, which is the implementation of social and socio-cultural influences, as well as the historical life of the people and the progress of human society as a whole, occupies a special place among the factors of language development. L. Bloomfield treats the phenomenon of borrowing, along with phonetic changes, as holding the leading role in the history of language (Bloomfield, 1968).

The complex issues of the interaction of language with other languages as a result of their joint history determine the specificity of language in each period of its history. Determining the history of language as the description of the evolution or historical development that has been interpreted as the gradual complication, and therefore improvement (Rastorgueva,

Materials and Methods

1989, p.28), in our work we accept the general concept of linguistic change, and based on this concept, the approach and methods of analysis of the material.

In our study, the communicative, functional-systemic and historical approaches to the language correspond to the study of the Middle English vocabulary according to the level of “common names” (with the nominative function) and “proper names esp. the bynames of the period of active formation of the system of surnames, which are the complex social-linguistic category and fulfil the nominative, identifying and social-judicial functions).

Etymological Classification of the Vocabulary

Classification of the vocabulary according to the etymology (the source of borrowing) is one of the most common ways of systematization of the vocabulary (along with the systematization according to chronology, semantics, structure and the degree of assimilation). One of the urgent tasks of the etymology is to reveal the ways of formation of the vocabulary of the English language, which helps to reproduce its etymological model. The use of the achievements of lexicography for multidimensional descriptions of lexical units (as well as the material of integrated linguistic studies of definite lexical strata) is based on such characteristics of modern lexicographical sources, as their clarity and depth of explanatory material, the brevity and generalization of definitions, as well as the presence of etymological notation, clarifying the word-building models of derivatives (Gromova, 2011, pp.38–39).

In this paper, the etymological model of the thematic group of Middle English names of occupation and office is construed on the basis of the analysis of the lexical material as to the linguistic identity of the derivational bases and derivatives, highlighting the native English vocabulary and borrowings. We distinguish the language of origin and the source of borrowing of the foreign words. We consider the lexical borrowings as to their nearest etymology (i.e., the source of their penetration into the English language), and their etymons are taken from the historical-etymological dictionaries of the Middle English language.

Functional Classification of the Vocabulary

Our paper is based on the communicative, functional-systemic and historical approaches to the language study – we treat the Middle English vocabulary according to the levels of “common names” and “proper names”: within each etymological group, we distribute the words along the functional lines, separating three categories of vocabulary: 1) the occupational terms that functioned only as appellatives (common names); 2) the occupational terms that functioned only as proper names; 3) the occupational terms that functioned both as appellatives, and as proper names. The following facts make us consider the occupational terms under study to be the words of non-occasional usage (i.e., meet the generally accepted usage): they were recorded in the Medieval written documents; their derivational basis is the English and assimilated borrowed vocabulary; their structure meets the rules and productive models of Middle English word-formation; their spelling corresponds to the Middle English orthographic rules. Basing on the distribution of vocabulary on the functional principle and its quantitative estimation, we draw the conclusions about the degree of usualness of the vocabulary under study esp. its sustainability): 1) the occupational terms that functioned both as appellatives and the proper names are considered to be the words of the settled usage; 2) the occupational terms that functioned only as the proper names are considered to be the words of the unsettled usage; 3) the occupational terms that functioned only as appellatives are considered to be the words of the limited usage.

Three closely related aspects of Medieval surnames – linguistic, social and historical – have led to their inclusion in the research material of Middle English occupational terms in the dissertation of T. Solonovich (Solonovich, 1986) esp. 1771 words denoting occupation were

taken from the Middle English Dictionary edited by Sherman M. Kuhn (1952–1983) (letters A–P) and the Middle English Dictionary edited by F. H. Stratmann (1951) (letters Q–Z), as well as the Medieval surnames noted in the financial and judicial documents of the XII–XIV centuries and collected in the following papers of linguists ekwall, 1947; Fransson, 1935; Mills, 1968; Otto, 1938; Thuresson, 1950).

Functional differentiation of Middle English occupational terms was not yet in the focus of linguistic studies, that is why we determined the **aim of our research** as the study of etymology, functional differentiation and chronological distribution of the occupational terms on the basis of new enriched **material** – Middle English Dictionary (as the part of Middle English Compendium) and Oxford English Dictionary (OED) – presupposing the fulfilment of the following **tasks**: 1. to collect occupational terms and present them in special way: appellatives – in the form of invariants, proper names – in the form of a phonographic variants; 2. to determine their etymology and group them according to it; 3. to investigate their functional differentiation and group them according to it; 4. to study the chronological distribution of the vocabulary under study; 5. to make absolute and relative quantitative analysis of these groups of the vocabulary.

We have grouped all the phonographic variants of occupational terms used as proper nouns and present them in chronological order of their usage; the first (in chronology) usage of the occupational term as common noun is presented in its invariant form; consequently we have investigated 2417 Middle English occupational terms, esp. 2013 words used as proper names (7429 phonographic variations of surnames in 10205 examples of their usage) and 404 words were only used as common nouns; among them the subgroup of the nouns denoting farm-workers, who were in charge of domestic animals, includes 157 words.

We would present the surnames without personal names, because they are irrelevant for the purpose of our investigation; the usage of small/ capital letter is given according to the literary source representing the absence of firm rules in Middle English orthography. The usage of occupational term as common noun is verified by its lexical-semantic variant given in the Middle English Dictionary and Oxford English Dictionary with precise dating of its first usage.

English occupational terms:

1 herdsmen (in general): *Drivere* 1275, 1279, 1283, *Driveres* 1279, 1301, *Driuere* 1332, *Driver* 1340, *Dryver* 1380, *Dryvere* 1407, *Dryver* 1491 (*drivere one who drives or looks after livestock*; *herdsman, drover* 1391 MED); *Drouere* 1287–93, 1294, *Drovere* 1327, 1384, *Drouer* 1436, *drover* 1463 (*drovere one who drives livestock to market, a dealer in livestock*; *drover* 1393–4 MED; *one who drives droves of cattle, sheep, etc.; esp. to distant markets; a dealer in cattle* 1425 OED); *Feeman* 1282 (*fē-man a herdsman* 1400 MED); *gresman* 1391 (*gras-man some kind of tenant of a manor, a grazier, a cottager* 1153 MED; *gras* n. early) *græs & grēse, gresse, grece* – MED); *Hirdman* 1166, *Hyrdeman* 1181, *Erdman* 1260, *Herdman* 1296 (*hērde-man [OE] a shepherd; a tender of goats, cattle, horses, or other livestock; a herdsman* 1200 MED); *Lehird* 1221, *Hord* 1221, *herde* 1222, *Herde* 1222, 1308, 1327, 1481, *Hirde* 1227, 1297, 1355, *Herd* 1243, 1329, *Heyrde* 1275, *Hurde* 1275, 1296, 1333, *Hird* 1327, *Hierde* 1327 (*hērde [OE] a herdsman; a keeper of cattle, hogs, horses, goats, or any kind of livestock* 1150 MED, 725 OED); *Hyne* 1278, 1286, 1313, 1327, 1328, 1346, 1392, *Hine* 1297, 1332 (*hīne [OE] a farm laborer, herdsman, shepherd, etc.* 1200 MED); *Kepere* 1279, 1281, 1327, 1367 (*kēpere one who takes care of animals; a shepherd, herdsman, beekeeper, etc.* 1393 MED); *Iedere* 1243, *leeder* 1328 (*lēdere an animal keeper* 1385 MED, *one who has the charge of animals* 1495 OED); *Loker* 1221, *Lokar* 1279, *Lokere* 1296, *Lokar* 1327, *Louker* 1327 (*looker one who looks after or has charge of anything, e.g. children, cattle, land, a farm,*

Results and Discussion

Occupational Terms with the Settled Usage

woods, etc.): a guardian, keeper, shepherd, farm-bailiff, steward 1340 OED, lōkere~of bestes a herdsman 1400 MED); *Netdriver* 1295 (nēt~ drīvere 1440 MED, nēt [OE neat] livestock; esp. bovine animals, cattle 1131 MED, drīvere (< driven [OE drīfan]) one who drives or looks after livestock; herdsman, drover 1391 MED); *Waterer* 1443 (wātrēr a person responsible for watering animals 1500 MED);

2 keepers of cattle: *Dai* 1196, *Daye* 1251, 1263, 1269, 1294, 1301, 1327, *Dey* 1286, *Deye* 1327, 1387, *Daie* 1346 (daie a woman who keeps cows and other farm stock 1209 MED; a man in charge of the dairy cattle and other farm stock, dairyman 1271 MED); *Melkere* 1250, 1296, *Milker* 1254, 1327, *Milkar* 1255, 1279, *Melkare* 1327, *Melker* 1332 (milker a milker, one who milks cows 1500 MED); *Nethirde* 1301, *Netehird* 1301, *Nethird* 1332, 1353 (nēt-hērde a cowherd 1384 MED, neatherd one who has the care of neat cattle, a cowherd 1382 OED, nēt [OE nēat] & hērde); *Oxhirde* 1281, *Oxhird* 1325, *Oxehird* 1327, *Oxherd* 1332, *Ocsehurde* 1385 (oxe-herde a keeper of oxen; a herdsman 1398 MED, a keeper of oxen; a cowherd 1000 OED); *Rotherherde* 1276, *Retherherde* 1294, *Rutherherde* 1299, *Rozerherd* 1316 (rother-herde [OE hrīðer-hirde] herdsman 1225 MED);

3 keepers of pigs: *ogger* 1327, *Hogger* 1327, *Hoggere* 1329, *Ogger* 1427 (hoggere a herdsman; swineherd, shepherd 1400 MED); *Hoggehird* 1279, *Hoghird* 1327, *Hogherde* 1327, *Hoggard* 1461 (hogge-herde a swineherd or a shepherd 1400 MED; a swineherd 1380 OED); *Swon* 1215, 1303, 1327, 1350–51, *Swan* 1246, *Suon* 1282, *Swoun* 1296–7, *Swoon* 1366 (swōn a swineherd 1325 MED);

4 keepers of horses: *Horsknaue* 1282, *Horsecnaue* 1307, *Horsknaue* 1317 (hors~knave stableboy, groom 1300 MED); *Horshirde* 1301, *Horshird* 1309, *Horsherd* 1331 (hors~herde one who tends horses, a horsekeeper, hostler, innkeeper 1225 MED); *Horseleche* 1418, *horseleche* 1463–4 (hors-lēche a horse doctor 1418 MED); *Horsman* 1227, 1332, 1396–7, *Horseman* 1248, *Horsmon* 1275, *Horsemon* 1332, 1428, *horseman* 1450 (hors-man a horse keeper, stable man, groom 1400 MED);

5 keepers of sheep: *Flocker* 1302 (flokker a shepherd 1425 MED); *ogger* 1327, *Hogger* 1327, *Hoggere* 1329, *Ogger* 1427 (hoggere a herdsman; swineherd, shepherd 1400 MED, hog [OE] a swine; esp. a castrated male swine; a young sheep before the first shearing MED, a swine reared for slaughter 1175 OED); *Hoggehird* 1279, *Hoghird* 1327, *Hogherde* 1327, *Hoggard* 1461 (hogge-herde a swineherd or a shepherd 1400 MED); *Cepherd* 1266, *Sepherd* 1279, 1294, *Schepherde* 1279, 1297, *Sephurde* 1279, 1296, *Scephurde* 1281, *Ssepherd* 1294, *Sepherde* 1296, *Sepeherd* 1302, *Shepperde* 1307, *Schiphird* 1307, *Shipherde* 1317, *Shepehird* 1319, 1426–27, *Schephierd* 1325, *Sheparde* 1327, *Shepehird* 1327, *Cepherde* 1327, *Shipherde* 1327, *Shuphurde* 1327, *Shuppurd* 1327, *Schephurde* 1327, *Scheipherde* 1327, *Cheyphurde* 1327, *Cephurde* 1327, *Cephurde* 1327, *Shepherd* 1328, *Shephard* 1330, *Scephirde* 1332, *Shepharde* 1332, *shepurde* 1332, *Shipurde* 1333, *Shippurde* 1333, *Sephirde* 1341, *Shephurde* 1351, *Shipherd* 1443, *scheperde* 1460 (shĕp-hĕrde [OE scĕap-hirde] 1023 OED); *Schepherdes* 1311, *Sheperdes* 1327 (shĕp-hĕrdes(se a female keeper of sheep; also, the wife of a shepherd 1393 MED); *Scherher* 1272, *Scherar* 1284, *Scherer* 1305, *Schirere* 1305, *sherar* 1318–19, *Sherare* 1327, *Sherere* 1363, 1445, *Sherer* 1396 (shĕrere a shearer of sheep 1395 MED);

6 keepers of poultry: *Goseherd* 1236, *Gosehurde* 1290, *Goshurde* 1327, *Gusehyrd* 1485 (gōs~herd one who tends a flock of geese 1440 MED, 14. OED).

Derivatives from the assimilated loanwords of Old French origin: *Palfreyman* 1264, 1279, 1365–6, *Palfayman* 1332, *Palframon* 1332, *Palfreman* 1333, *Paleframon* 1351, *Pallefrayman* 1387, *Palframman* 1379 (palefrei~man groom 1400 MED, palefrei [OF palefroi, palefrei, paulefroi & ML pale]fridus, ~fredus; cp. CL paraverēdus) a riding horse (as opposed to a war horse); a fine riding horse 1200 MED; a saddle-horse for ordinary riding as distinguished from a war-horse; esp. a small saddle-horse for ladies 1175 OED; *palfrey-man* 1297; cf. *palfrenier* [F palefrenier 1350] a man having charge of horses; a groom 1489 OED; cf. *palefreiður* one who

takes care of riding horses, a palfrey man, groom 1325 MED); *palfraypage* 1360–1, *Palfraypage* 1385 (palefrei–pāģe horse boy, stableboy 1358 MED; palefrei [OF palefroi, palefrei, paulefroi & ML pale, fridus, -fredus; cp. CL paraverēdus] a riding horse (as opposed to a war horse); a fine riding horse 1200 MED; pāģe [OF]) a groom, stableboy; servant to tend livestock 1325 ME; an assistant to a shepherd 1410 MED).

Derivatives from the assimilated loanwords of Scandinavian origin: *Geldehyrd* 1284, *Geildehirde* 1298, *Geldehirde* 1317, *Geldhurd* 1319 (geldherd one who tended the geld cattle 1317 OED; gelde-hirde a herdsman who tends to the gelded cattle MED, geld [ON; cp. OI geldr] geld~hors a gelding; geld~gris, geld ~hogge a barrow; geld~ram, geld~shep a wether, gelding n. [ON; cp. OI geldingr] a gelded horse, gelding, hērde [OE] a herdsman); *Cliper* 1300, 1327 (clipper a sheepshearer 1382 MED, *clippen* [ON; cp. OI klippa] cut hair; to shear (sheep); to clip or mutilate (a coin); to shape or engrave (dies used in minting money)); *Mukere* 1229, *Muker* 1276, *Moker* 1296, 1327, *Moukor* 1332 (mukker one who cleans stables, a manure hauler 1475 MED, *mukken* (< muk n. [ON; cp. OI myki dung & Norw. dial. mukka a heap] animal or human excrement; dung; manure; also, dirt, filth; sewage; putrescence; also cp. OI moka v.) to spread manure; fertilize (plants, land) with manure; prepare land for planting; also, remove dung (from a place), haul manure; to dig in the ground); *noutehird* 1296, *Nouthirde* 1301, 1328, *Nauthird* 1309, *Nautherde* 1316, *Noutehirde* 1327–30, *nouthird* 1327, *Noutherd* 1340 (nōut-hērde a cowherd 1450 MED, 1330 OED, nōute [ON; cp. OI naut] an ox, a bull).

Loanwords of Latin origin: *Corser* 1227, 1449, *Coursour* 1313, *corsor* 1383, *corser* 1440 (corser [ML cursor trader, broker] a horse trainer 1439 MED).

Loanwords of Old French (Central French) origin: *Geynur* 1268, *ganyer* 1279, *Gaynere* 1319 (gaineier [OF gäaigneör, gäaineur, gäaigniere] a farmer 1440 MED); *Marescal* 1084, *Maskercal* 1087–97, *Marescald* 1100–30, *Mascherell* 1130, *mareschall* 1140, *Maskerel* 1166, *Marshal* 1218, *Mareschall* 1222, *Marscal* 1238, *Mareschale* 1242, *Mareschal* 1270, 1333, 1355, *Marechal* 1287–8, *Marschal* 1296, *marchal* 1308, *Marchale* 1314, *mareschal* 1350–51, *Marchall* 1386, *marsshall* 1428, 1464 (marshal [OF mareschal, marescal, marechal, from Gmc.] a farrier, a horse doctor; also, a stable officer, master of horses 1308 MED; one who tends horses, esp. one who treats their diseases, a farrier 1130 OED; with sb. prefixed as sergeant-, valet-, yeoman-ferrer: An official who had care of the horses in a large household 1455 OED); p.1234, 1236, 1240, 1250–1, 1275, 1296–7, 1327–8, 1351, p.1454 (pāģe [OF]) a groom, stableboy; servant to tend livestock 1325 ME; an assistant to shepherd 1410 MED); *Pasturel* 1166, 1303 (pastorēl [OF] a herdsman 1400 MED).

Loanwords with double (Latin/ French) etymology: *pastor* 1140–53, *Pastur* 1227, 1242, 1250, 1258, 1431, *Pastor* 1265, 1293, *Pastour* 1317, 1327 (pastōur [OF pastor & L pastor, -ōris] a shepherd or herdsman 1376 MED (AF pastour, OF pastor, pastur herdsman, shepherd. In early sources *pastor* is often Lat *pastor* shepherd; pastor (pastour, -oure, -ure, pastor) [ME and AF pastour = OF pastor, pastur, L pastōr-em shepherd, lit. feeder, giver of pasture]) a herdsman or shepherd 1362 OED).

Motivated loanwords of Old French (Central French) origin: *Grangier* 1173, 1230–40, *Granger* 1223, *Graunger* 1231, 1390, *Grainger* 1246, *Grangir* 1272, *Greunger* 1275, *Gronger* 1279, *Grangere* 1325 (graunger [OF grangier] a granger, a man in charge of a grange 1195 MED).

Motivated loanwords of Old French (Norman) origin: *Palfreur* 1246, *Palefreur* 1255, *Palefreur* 1260, *Palfreyur* 1269, *Palefreyur* 1276, *Palefrayur* 1285, *Palefayor* 1297, *Palefreour* 1305, *palefreiour* 1319, *palfreyur* 1301, *Palfreyour* 1310 (palefreiōur [AF] one who takes care of riding horses, a palfrey man, groom 1325 MED, palefrei [OF palefroi, palefrei, paulefroi & ML pale]fridus, -fredus; cp. CL paraverēdus] a riding horse as opposed to a war horse; a fine

riding horse 1200 MED); *palfreyour* (*palfreur*, *palefreyur*, *palefreiour*, *palfreour*, *palfrer*) [AF *palefreyur*] = *palfrenier* 1297 OED; *palfrenier* [F *palefrenier*, also *pare-*, *palfrenier*] *a man having charge of horses; a groom* 1489 OED; *palfrey* (*palfre*) [ME, OF *palefrei*] *a saddle-horse for ordinary riding as distinguished from a war-horse; esp. a small saddle-horse for ladies* 1175 OED, cf. *palfrey-man* 1297).

Motivated loanwords with double (Latin/ French) etymology: *Fermer* 1328, *Farmere* 1279, *Fermor* 1293 (*farmer* [AF *fermer*, F *fermier*: – med. L *firmārius*, OE *farm sb2*, *farm v2* + *-er*] *one who rents land for the purpose of cultivation* = *tenantfarmer* 1487 OED; *one who cultivates land for the owner; a bailiff, a steward* 1382 OED; *farm*, sb. [F *ferme*, ML *firma fixed payment*] *a fixed yearly amount payable as rent, tax, or the like* 1400 OED; *a fixed yearly sum accepted from a person as a composition for taxes or other moneys which he is impowered to collect* 1386 OED; *a lease* 1500 OED; *farm*, v. [*< sb2*] *to take or hold for a term at a fixed payment a) to rent (land, etc.)* 1440 OED); *Hostiler* 1190, *Osteler* 1204, 1260, 1360, *Ostler* 1204, *Osteyler* 1230, *Ostiller* 1254, *Oystler* 1258, *Hostler* 1275, *Hosteler* 1296, 1301, 1381, *Husteler* 1301, *Hostiller* 1330, *hostelere* 1350, *Osteler* 1360, *hostyller* 1365, *Hostelere* 1381, *hosteler* 1385, *Hostyler* 1410, *hostillare* 1432 (*höstilĕr* [AF *hostiler* & OF *hostelier* & ML *hostellārius*, *hostilārius*] *an innkeeper or lodging house keeper, the master or mistress of an inn* MED; *a brothel keeper* 1400 MED; *a servant at an inn; esp. one who attends horses, a stableman; also, one who keeps horses for hire, a horse dealer* 1390 MED); *ostler* (*osteler*, *-eller*, *-iler*, *-elere*, *-elore*, *-ostler*, *oastler*) [a phonetic spelling of *Hosteler*, *Hostler*, representing the historical pronunciation with *h* mute. In earlier times it was frequent also in the sense “keeper of a hostelry” (see *hosteler*); but since 16th c. has been restricted generally to the following sense, in which it is also (now less frequent) spelt *hostler*. In the 1st Fol. of *Shaks.* *ostler* appears six times, *hostler* once, but the latter was more frequent in 18th c.] *a man who attends to horses at an inn; a stableman, a groom* 1386 OED); (OF *ostelier*, *hostelier*, ME (h)*ostiler*, (h)*osteler* *one who receives, lodges or entertains guests, especially in a monastery* 1290 OED, *keeper of a hostelry or inn* 1365 OED); *Stabler* 1196, 1218–19, 1261, *Establer* 1257, *Stablere* 1281, *Stabeler* 1301, 1401–2, *Stabiler* 1327, *Stablier* 1327, *Stabelere* 1391 (*stäbler* [OF *establier*, *establer*, *вѣд estable*, *pop. L. stabulārius*] *a stable-keeper; also, a hostler* 1454 MED, *a stable-keeper* 14. OED, *stāble* [OF *estable*, L *stabulum*] *a building for the keeping of animals, esp. horses, a stable* 1216 MED).

Occupational Terms with the Unsettled Usage

The meaning of the word is presupposed on the basis of its usage as a surname and is given in the dictionaries without dating, being reconstructed by the lexicographers and marked as *in surnames, as surnames, only as surname*.

English occupational terms:

1 herdsmen (in general): *Auerhurde* 1327 (*āver~hurde* *a servant who tends horses* MED); *Borwherd* 1276 (*burgh~herd* *a town herdsman* MED); *Deyman* 1428 (**daie~man* *dairyman (as surname)* – MED, *daie* [OE *dæge*, *-an* (corresp. to OI *daigja*)] *a woman in charge of milking and making butter and cheese, a dairymaid; daie* *a man in charge of the dairy cattle and other farm stock, dairyman*); *Drencher* 1327 (*drencher (only as surname)* *one who waters cattle* MED); *Feemaister* 1458 (*fee~master* *one in charge of the flocks and herds* DBS); *Floteman* 1215, 1524 (*floatman* *a man who manages a float* 1882 OED); *Fodere* 1327, *Fodere* 1327, *Fodier* 1332 (*fōden* v. [from *fōde*] *to supply with food, to feed; nurse, foster* 1225 MED; cp. *feeder* *one who feeds up or fattens (an animal), esp. one whose business it is to feed cattle for slaughter* 1430 OED, MED; *fēdere* *one who feeds, sustains, or supports* MED); *Grasier* 1275, *Grasiere* 1279, 1337, *Garsere* 1305, *Grasyer* 1446, *grasier* 1437 (*grāsier* *one who grazes cattle, a grazier* MED, *gras* (*gars*) MED); *Herder* 1327, *Herdere* 1332, *Hurder* 1333 (*hērder* *a herdsman, only as surname* MED, *one who herds; a herdsman* 1635 OED); *Herdeman* 1367 (*herdsman* *a keeper of domestic animals which go in herd, esp. of cattle*

1603 OED); *Lockhart* 1203 (*herdsman in charge of the sheep or cattlefold* DBS); *Lokward* 1319, *Locward* 1327 (*in surnames* – MED); *Medherd* 1317 (*in surnames* – MED, *herd in charge of grazing cattle* DBS); *Milkster* 1246 (**milkster* cf. *milkere milk vendor* 1500 MED, *a milker, one who milks cows* 1500 MED, *one who milks (cows, etc.); one who draws milk from the udders of cattle* 1475 OED); *Penner* 1327 (*worker at the fold* DBS); *Tunherd* 1279, *Tunherd* 1327 (OE **tūn-hierde guardian of the village or town animals* DBS); *Wodehirde* 1275, *Wodehirde* 1325 (*one who tends animals feeding in a wood; probably 'a swineherd* DBS);

2 keepers of cattle:

a) cows: *Cuward* 1198, *cuherde* 1222, 1254, *Cuherde* 1255, 1296, *Couhyrde* 1268, 1287, *Cuhirde* 1279, *Kuherde* 1274, *Cuhurd* 1281, *Couhyrd* 1281, *Kuherde* 1287, *Couhirde* 1301, *Couherde* 1309, 1317, *Couherd* 1317, 1357, *Couhurde* 1327, 1332, *Couharde* 1327, *Cowherde* 1327, *Kouherd* 1332, *kouhirde* 1332, *Couhierde* 1332, *Cowhyrd* 1333–4, *Cowherd* 1360 (*cōu-hērde* [OE] *one who tends cows, a cowherd* MED, **cū-weard* [OE] *cow-guard* *one whose occupation is to tend cows at pasture* 1000 OED); *Cowman* 1404–5 (*in surnames* MED); *Kynewarde* 1244 (*in surnames* – MED; *cōu.* (pl. *kīn*) MED);

b) bulls and oxen: *Bollocherd* 1281, *Bollochurde* 1327, *Bullokhirde* 1330 (*bullok~herde a keeper of bullocks or steers* MED); *Bullokman* 1332 (*bullok~man a keeper of bullocks or steers* MED); *Oxeman* 1201, *Oxeman* 1289 (*in surnames* – MED, *oxman a man who looks after oxen, a herdsman* 1830 OED); *retherdryver* 1396 (*rother~drivere a cattle driver* MED, *rother* [OE *hrīðer, hrȳðer, LOE hrūper*; cp. *LOE hreoðarhyrde*] *an ox, a cow, bull* MED);

c) calves: *Calfherd* 1263, 1302–3, 1310, *Kalfhirde* 1263, *Calfhirde* 1269, *Calvehird* 1285, 1297, 1382, *Calvehirde* 1297, *Calfhurd* 1301, *Calverde* 1309, *Calfhird* 1401, *Calferde* 1445, *Calverd* 1472 (*calf~herd herdsman who takes care of calves, as surnames* – MED, *the calf-herd* DBS); *Kalveknave* 1247, *Calueknave* 1284, *Calveknave* 1301 (*calf~knave, calves~knave herdsman who takes care of calves, as surnames* – MED); *Caluerknave* 1327 (*calver~knave herdsman who takes care of calves, as surnames* – MED); *Caluesknave* 1327 (*calves~knave herdsman who takes care of calves, as surnames* – MED); *Sterherd* 1332 (*in surnames* – MED, *stēre* [OE *stēor*] *a young bull or ox, bullock*); *Styirleche* 1299 (*in surnames* – MED); *Stirkehirde* 1301, *Strikhirde* 1327, *Stirkerd* 1428 (*in surnames* – MED, *stirk* [OE *stirc*] *a young bullock or heifer*);

3 keepers of pigs: *Bareward* 1246, *Boreward* 1313, 1317, 1333, *Borward* 1327 (*bōr~ward keeper of boars, swineherd* MED); *Forward* 1279, *Foreward* 1279, *Forewardes* 1327 (*swineherd* DBS); *Hoggeman* 1301, *Hogeman* 1327, 1392 (*in surnames* – MED); *Hoggreue* 1332 (*in surnames* – MED); *Pigman* 1190 (*in surnames* – MED, *pigge* [OE **pigga*]); *Pyghurde* 1327 (*in surnames* – MED); *Sueherd* 1379 (*sow~herd* DBS, *sōue, sou(we, -sue, OE sū a female swine, sow* MED);

4 keepers of horses: *Coltehird* 1301, *Colthird* 1359 (*colt~hirde one who tends colts, as surnames* – MED, *keeper of colts* DBS); *Coltier* 1285, *Coltere* 1327 (*a keeper of colts* DBS); *Coltman* 1322, 1332, 1461, *Coltmon* 1365 (*one who tends colts, as surnames* – MED, *a keeper of colts* DBS); *Horsdriver* 1273 (*in occupational surnames* – MED); *Stodhyrda* 1195, *Stodhurd* 1219, *Stodhirde* 1286, *Stodehard* 1332, *Studherd* 1450, *Stoderd* 1481, *Stodard* 1482 (*stōde~herde the keeper of a stud* MED); *Stodman* 1297, 1332 (*studman a servant attached to the stud* 1545 OED);

5 keepers of sheep: *faulder* 1332 (*folder one who folds sheep; a shepherd* 1571 OED); *Yowehirde* 1297, *Ewehurde* 1327, *Yewhird* 1332, *Ewehird* 1379, *Yowarde* 1381, *Owherde* 1424 (*eue~herde, owherd shepherd* MED; *keeper of the dairy-farm* DBS, *eue* [OE *ēowu*] *a female sheep; mother sheep*); *Hoggeman* 1301, *Hogeman* 1327, 1392 (*in surnames* – MED); *Hoggreue* 1332 (*in surnames* – MED); *Lambhyrde* 1255, *Lambhurde* 1288, *Lambehird* 1309, *Lomherde* 1327, *Lambeherde* 1332, *Lompharde* 1332, *Lambhird* 1380 (*in surnames* – MED, *lōmb* [OE *lamb*] 725 OED); *Lambegrom* 1279, *Lambergrom* 1279 (*in surnames* – MED); *Schepdriure* 1294 (*in surnames* – MED); *Schepgrom* 1327, *Schipgrom* 1341 (*in surnames* – MED, *a*

shepherd or a dealer in sheep DBS); *Scipman* 1221, *Sipman* 1267, *Schipman* 1290, *Schepman* 1296, *Schepman* 1316, *Schapman* 1332 (*in surnames* – MED, *sheepman a shepherd* 1591 OED); *schepreve* 1397, *sheperefe* 1450, *Shepereve* 1445 (*shĕp-reve an overseer of sheep, a principal shepherd* MED); *Shepeward* 1329, *Shipward* 1357, 1471, *Shypward* 1432 (*in surnames* – MED, *sheepward a shepherd* 1609 OED); *Toppare* 1275, *Tupper* 1314, *Toppere* 1327 (*the surname may also be a late form of tup-herd* DBS, *tup(pe [OE] a male sheep, ram)*); *Tophird* 1327, *Tuphird* 1379 (*in surnames* – MED); *Wassere* 1293, *Wascere* 1295 (*washer one who washes sheep before shearing* 1520 OED); *Wethyrhyrde* 1200, *Wetherherde* 1214, *Wetherhirde* 1297, *Wetherherde* 1417, *Weydurherd* 1476, *Wedirhed* 1476 (*in surnames* – MED; *shepherd* DBS, *wether [OE] a male sheep, ram*);

6 keepers of goats: *Bukkeman* 1278 (*goat-keeper* DBS, *bukke [OE bucca] the adult male-goat, he-goat*);

7 keepers of poultry: *Gosman* 1247, *Goceman* 1301 (*gōs-man one who tends a flock of geese* MED); *Henneman* 1274, *Henman* 1327, *Heneman* 1327 (*in surnames* – MED, *man in charge of the hens* DBS).

Derivatives from the assimilated loanwords of Latin origin: *Mulegrom* 1327 (*mūle-grom a mulekeeper, servant who takes care of mules, in surnames* – MED, *mule [OE mūl (from L), OF mule, ML moulus]*); *Muleman* 1315 (*mūle-man a mulekeeper, servant who takes care of mules, in surnames* – MED); *muleward* 1296–7 (*mūle-ward a mulekeeper, servant who takes care of mules, in surnames* – MED); *Stothard* 1279, *Stothirde* 1297, *Stothurd* 1306, *Stotard* 1317, *Stotherd* 1327 (*in surnames* MED, *keeper of horses or bullocks, oxherd* DBS; *stot [LOE stott & AL stottus] a bullock, steer; a horse, esp. one used for plowing; also, a stallion* MED, *stot [OE stot(t)] a horse; OE() one of an inferior kind* 1100 OED; *a young castrated ox, a steer (north)* 1251 OED; *a heifer (north)* 1371 OED).

Derivatives from the assimilated loanwords of Old French (Central) origin: *Bestere* 1279, *Bestare* 1311 (*beaster a herdsman* DBS; *beast (beste, best, beaste, beist, beaste, bieste, beise, beast) [F beste: – L bestia] OED*); *Besteman* 1327 (*bestman a herdsman, equivalent to Bester' DBS*); *Greser* 1327 (*grĕser < grĕsen v. one who smears a salve on sheep* MED, *grĕsen v. [from grĕse n] to apply a salve to (a sheep)* 1402 MED, *grĕse [AF grece, gresse; cp. CF craisse, gresse] 1300 MED*); *hoghalere* 1341 (*in surnames* – MED, *hālier (halere) a carrier, porter* MED, *hog(ge [OE] a swine, hālier (halere, haliher, hailer) < hālen v. [OF] a carrier, porter* MED); *Sowehaler* 1311, *Sowehaler* 1337 (*in surnames* – MED, *sōue [OE sugu, sū] a female swine, sow; hālier (halere, haliher, hailer) < hālen v. [OF] a carrier, porter* 1279 MED).

Derivatives with double (Latin/ French) etymology: *Motoner* 1275 (*motōner [from motōun. Any connection with F (XVI cent.) mutinier n. or mutiner v. is very unlikely] a shepherd, a dealer in mutton, a dealer in sheep* MED, *motōun [OF mouton, moton, motun, mutun, multon, multun & ML multo, moto, muto; ult. Celt.] the flesh of sheep, mutton* 1300 MED; *a sheep* 1325 MED); *mutton* (*motone, moton*) [ME *motoun, moton* (rarely *molton*), OF *moton*, rarely *molton* (mod. F *mouton*) – ML *multōn-em* (8th c.)] *the flesh of sheep, used as food* 1290 OED; *a sheep; esp.) one intended to be eaten* 1338 OED); *Multonman* 1332 (*in surnames* – MED; *motōun-man = motoner n. a shepherd, a dealer in mutton, a dealer in sheep* MED, *motōun [OF mouton, moton, motun, mutun, multon, multun & ML multo, moto, muto; ult. Celt.] the flesh of sheep, mutton* 1300 MED; *a sheep* 1325 MED); *Pasturherde* 1332 (*pastūre [OF (cp. CF pasture & AF pastour) & L pastūra] land on which animals graze, pastureland; a field, pasture* 1133–60 MED).

Derivatives from the assimilated loanwords of Scandinavian origin:

1 herdsmen (in general): *Geldehyrd* 1284, *Geildehirde* 1298, *Geldehirde* 1317, *Geldhurd* 1319 (*gelde-hirde a herdsman who tends to the gelded cattle* MED, *geldherd one who*

tended the geld cattle 1317 OED, *geld* [ON; cp. OI *geldr*] *geld~hors a gelding*; *geld-gris, geld ~hogge a barrow*; *geld~ram, geld~shap a wether*, *gelding n.* [ON; cp. OI *geldingr*] *a gelded horse, gelding*); *Latheman* 1278 (*in surnames* – MED, *worker at the barn(s)* DBS, *lāthe* [ON; cp. OI *hlaða.*] *a barn for livestock, grain, etc.; a granary; a storehouse*); *mukdragher* 1341 (*muk~drauer one who hauls manure* MED, cp. *mukker one who cleans stables, a manure hauler* 1475 MED, *muk n.* [ON; cp. OI *myki dung* & Norw. dial. *mukka a heap*] *animal or human excrement; dung; manure; dirt, filth; sewage; putrescence, drauere one who pulls, drags, or transports something* (from *drauen* [OE *dragan*, cp. OI *draga*]);

2 keepers of cattle: *Buleherte* 1190, *Bolherd* 1320 (*in surnames* – MED, *bōle* [ON, cp. OI *boli*, & OE **bula*] *a bull, hērde* [OE] *a herdsman*); *Blleward* 1319 (*in surnames* – MED, *ward* [OE *weard*] *a guard, sentinel; a guardian*); *Bulman* 1464 (*in surnames* – MED); *Quihird* 1301, *Whihird* 1332 (**quie~herd a herdsman of heifers* MED, *quie~ hērde* (quie [ON: cp. OI *kvīga*] *a young cow, heifer*);

3 keepers of goats: *Bucswayn* 1327 (*bukke~swain, in surnames* – MED, *a goat-herd* DBS, *bukke* [OE *bucca*] *the adult male goat, he-goat, swein* [ON: cp. OI *sveinn*] *a retainer, an attendant; a servant*); *Gatier* 1279, 1332, *Geytere* 1279, *Gater* 1279, 1301, *Goter* 1327, *Gotere* 1333 (**gōter* (gater) *a goatherd; – only as surname* MED, *gōt* [OE *gāt* & ON (cp. OI *geit*))] *a domesticated goat; a male goat*); *Gateman* 1183, *Gaytman* 1304, *Gooteman* 1455, *Goteman* 1462–3 (**gōt~man a goatherd* MED); *Gothirde* 1229, *Gateherde* 1275, *Gotehird* 1285, *Gaythirde* 1301, *Gaytehird* 1301, *Gaythurd* 1304, *Gateherde* 1327, *Gotherde* 1332, *Gayterd* 1466 (**gōt~herde* [OE *gāt-hyrde*] *a goatherd* MED, *one who tends goats* 1000 OED); *Gotegrom* 1335 (**gōt~grom a goatherd* MED, *grōm* [prob. OE **grōm*, **grōma*] *an infant boy; a boy; a youth, young man; a man; a male servant, attendant; a retainer* MED; *a servant who attends to horses* OED); *Gotenecherl* 1183 (*goatherd* DBS, *carl* [ON; cp. OI *karl*] *a serf, servant, slave; a freedman; a easant, a rustic* 1325 MED); *Kideman* 1221, *Kydeman* 1275 (*man in charge of the kids* DBS, *kide* [ON] *the young of a goat* 1200 OED, MED);

4 keepers of horses: *Capelman* 1327 (*capelman one who looks after horses* DBS, *capel* [ON; cp. OI *kapall* (ult. L *caballus*)] *a horse or gelding; a warhorse, cart horse, riding horse, etc.* 1300 MED; cf. *capel~clauer horse clawer, stable boy* 1325 MED);

5 keepers of pigs: *Galter* 1297, 1498 (*galter as surname: a keeper of swine* MED, *galt* [ON; cp. OI *göltr* & *galti*] *a boar; also, a barrow*);

6 keepers of poultry: *Goswayn* 1245 (*gōs~swein one who tends a flock of geese* MED, *gōs* [OE *gōs*] *a goose of any kind, swein* [ON: cp. OI *sveinn*] *a retainer, an attendant; a servant*).

Derivatives from the assimilated loanwords of Low German origin: *hachur* 1241, *Hetchere* 1296, *Haccher'* 1332, *Hecchere* 1332, *hatcher* 1423–4 (*hacchere one who looks after the hatching of eggs* MED, *hacchen v.* [OE **hæccan*, **heccan*, MHG *hecken* (of birds) *to mate*] *to bring forth young from eggs, hatch* 1216 MED; *to hatch* (young birds, spiders, serpents); also, *hatch or incubate* 1382 MED).

Derivatives from the assimilated loanwords of Celtic origin: *Teghurde* 1396 (*shepherd* DBS, *teg, tag*, [Sc.] *a sheep in its second year* 1537 OED).

Loanwords with double (Latin/ French) etymology: *Bercharius* 1166, *Berchier* 1166, *Berker* 1185, *berkier* 1193, *Bercher* 1212, 1275, 1296, 1343, *berker* 1218–9, *Berechir* 1248, *Berkyr* 1266, *Berecher* 1287, *Berchar* 1317, *bercarius* 1327, *Bercar* 1328, *Bercheir* 1332, *Bercer* 1332, *Bergier* 1347–8 (*bercher* [AF; ML *bercarius*] *a shepherd* MED; OF *berchier, bercher, berkier, berker shepherd* DBS. OF also had the form *barcher*. Later, when ME *-er* had become *-ar*, *barker shepherd* would be indistinguishable in form from *barker tanner* DBS).

Motivated loanwords of Old French origin: *conreor* 1220, *Curur* 1256, *Coureer* 1281, *Conreur* 1286, *couraour* 1293, *Coureur* 1314, *Currayour* 1340, *Cunreyour* 1344, *corayour*

Occupational Terms with Limited Usage

1360, *Curreyour* 1375–6, *Curreour* 1375–6, *Curreior* 1375–6, *corear* 1395, *Curier* 1400, *Curryar* 1546 (*currier one who carries horses, etc.* 1562 OED, *conreeur*, *couraieur* [OF] *currier* (from OF *conreer*, *courroyer* to *curry*), *curreien* v. [AF *curreier*, CF *corroier* *prepare, take care of*] to *clean and comb (a horse)*, *curry* 1300 MED).

Motivated loanwords with double (Latin/ French) etymology: *Ferrur* 1196, *Ferur* 1200, *Farrou* 1379 (*ferrer* (*ferour*, *ferour*, *-oure*, *farrou*, *ferer*, *-owre*, *ferrur*, *farrer*, *ferrar*) [OF *ferreor*, *ferour* (F *ferreur*), med. L *ferratōr-em*] *one who treats the disease of horses* 1562 OED).

English occupational terms: *capel~clauer one who carries horses* (1325 MED); (*clauer* < *clauen* [OE *clawan*] *a scratcher*); *fēdere* [from *fēden* [OE *fēdan*]] *one who feeds, sustains, or supports* (1398 MED); *hērdesse* [from *hērde*] *a shepherdess* (1385 MED); *hors~kepere horse keeper, stableman* (1440 MED); *lēdere* [OE *lædere*] *an animal keeper* (1385 MED); *oxe~keper one who tends oxen pasturer* ([OE *oxa*]) (1400 MED); *pigge~takere a provider of swine for household consumption* (*pigge* [OE **pigga*]) (1454 MED); *swōn~herde* [OE *swān*] *a swineherd* (1400 MED); *tēchere* (*techour*) [from *tēchen* v. [OE *tæcan*]] *an animal trainer; also, someone who accustoms a pack animal to a route* (1408 MED).

Derivatives with double (Latin/ French) etymology: *mūle~herde a mulekeeper, servant who takes care of mules* 1475 MED, *mūle* [OE *mūl* (from L) & OF *mule* & ML *moulus.*] *a mule*).

Derivatives from the assimilated loanwords of Scandinavian origin: *geldere* [from *gelden*] *one who gelds livestock* (1425 MED); *gelden* v. [ON; cp.OI *gelda.*] *to castrate (a male animal); to spay (a sow)*.

Motivated loanwords of Latin origin: *mūliōn* [L *mūlio*] *a mule-keeper* 1422 MED.

Motivated loanwords with double (Latin/ French) etymology: *lābōur* [L & OF *labor*] *laborer, farm laborer, unskilled worker* 1425 MED.

In Table 1 we give the absolute and relative quantity of the etymological and functional groups of the occupational terms, denoting medieval farm-workers, who took care of domestic animals.

We have studied 157 words belonging to the thematic group of Middle English names of farm-workers, who were in charge of domestic animals, comprising 6.5 % of the total number of Middle English occupational terms. It was found out that 90 % of them are English words

Table 1

Etymology and usage of the Middle English names of farm-workers, who were in charge of domestic animals

Usage/ etymology	En	Derivatives (loan-blends)						Loan-words			Motivated loan-words			Total	%
		L	L/F	F	S	LG	C	L	L/F	F	L	L/F	F		
Settled	32	–	–	2	3	–	–	1	1	4	–	3	2	48	31
Unsettled	62	4	3	5	17	1	1	–	1	–	–	1	1	96	61
Limited	9	–	1	–	1	–	–	–	–	–	1	1	–	13	8
Total	103	38						7			9			157	100
%	66	24						4			6			100	

(24 % of them are loan-blends), 10 % are loan-words (of Latin, French or double (Latin / French) origin). The ratio of English words and loan-words is 9:1.

Functional distribution of the vocabulary within three groups of occupational terms gives the following results: those functioning as common nouns as well as the proper names (the words with the established usage) constitute 31 %; those functioning exclusively as the proper names in the personal nomination formulas (the words with the unsettled usage) constitute 61 %; those functioning exclusively as common nouns (the words with the restricted usage) constitute 8 %.

The most common is the division of the history of the English language into old English (449–1066), Middle English (1066–1475) and New English (1476 up till now) (King, 1979, p.54). In our study of chronological stratification of the Middle English names of herdsmen is fulfilled within the XIth–XVth centuries. The first written fixation of the vocabulary under study is given in Table 2.

Usage/ etymology	En	Derivatives (loan-blends)						Loan-words			Motivated loan-words			Total	%	
		L	L/F	F	S	LG	C	L	L/F	F	L	L/F	F			
OE	6														6	4
XI										1					1	1
XII	5				3				2	1		3	1		15	9.5
XIII	46	2	1	2	9	1		1		2			2		66	42
XIV	36	2	2	5	7		1					1			54	34
XV	10		1		2							1	1		15	9.5
Total	103	38						7			9			157	100	

The above given chronological stratification of the lexical-thematic subgroup of the Middle English names of farm-workers, who were in charge of domestic animals, indicates its predominant filling in the thirteenth century (42 %) and in the XIVth century (54 %).

The new data concerning the occupational terms of the Middle English language undoubtedly confirm the feasibility of using onomastic material in the study of the vocabulary of previous times, in particular to describe an objective picture of the etymological foundations of the lexical structure of the language, to understand the spheres of influence and future circulation of lexical borrowings.

The study of the vocabulary in different functions of their usage (nominative and identifying) enriched the content of Middle English thematic group of farm-workers with the new words and the following characteristics: etymological composition, esp. the predominance of the native english and loan-blends) over the loanwords in the ratio 9:1; functional differentiation and sustainability of usage, esp. the predominance of the vocabulary with the unsettled (non-established) usage; the predominance of the vocabulary with identifying function acting as the proper names additional to the personal name in the personal nomination formulas, over the vocabulary functioning exclusively as common nouns with the nominative function, with the ratio 9:1, which is the indication of the popularity of these words.

Table 2

Chronological stratification of the Middle English names of farm-workers, who took care of domestic animals

Conclusions and Perspectives

Abbreviations

- A** – Anglian dialects of Old English,
AF – Anglo-French,
AL – Anglo-Latin,
AN – Anglo-Norman,
Celt. – Celtic,
CF – Central French,
CL – Classical (as opposed to Medieval or Neo-) Latin,
DBS – Reaney, P. H. A Dictionary of British Surnames,
E – English,
F – French,
Gmc. – Germanic,
L – Latin,
LOE – Late Old English,
ME – Middle English,
MED – Middle English Compendium,
MHG – Middle High German,
ML – Medieval Latin,
mod. French – Modern French,
Norw. – Norwegian,
OE – Old English,
OED – Oxford English Dictionary,
OF – Old French,
OI – Old Icelandic,
ON – Old Norse,
WS – West Saxon dialect of Old English.

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Functional Groups of the Middle English Names of Farm-workers, Who Took Care of Domestic Animals

Appendix 1

In Appendix 1 the functional groups of the Middle English names of farm-workers are presented in alphabetical order.

Settled usage	Unsettled usage	Limited usage
daie > <i>Dagean, Daia, Dai, Deie, Daye, Dey, Daie, Deye</i>	*äver~hērde > <i>Auerhurde</i>	capel~clauer
clipper > <i>Cliper</i>	*bercher > <i>Bercharius, Berchier, Berker, berkier, Bercher, berker, Berechir, Berkyr, Berecher, Berchar, bercarius, Bercar, Bercheir, Bercer, Bergier</i>	fēdere
corser > <i>Corser, Coursour, corsor, corser</i>	*bēste-man > <i>Besteman</i>	geldere
drīvere > <i>Drivere, Driveres, Driuere, Driver, Dryver, Dryvere, Dryver</i>	*bēster > <i>Bestere Bestare</i>	hērdesse
drovere > <i>Drouere, Drovere, Drouer, drover</i>	*bōle~hērde > <i>Buleherte, Bolherd</i>	hors~kepere
farmer > <i>Fermer, Farmere, Fermor</i>	*bōle~ward > <i>Blleward</i>	lābōur
fēman > <i>Feeman</i>	*bōleman > <i>Bulman</i>	lēdere
flokker > <i>Flocker</i>	*bōr~ward > <i>Bareward, Boreward, Borward</i>	mūle~herde
gaïneier > <i>Geynur, ganyer, Gaynere</i>	*bukke-man > <i>Bukkeman</i>	mūliōn
geld~hērde > <i>Geldehyrd, Geildehirde, Geldehirde, Geldhurd</i>	*bukke~swein > <i>Bucswayn</i>	oxe~keper
gōs~herd > <i>Goseherd, Gosehurde, Goshurde, Gusehyrd</i>	*bullok~hērde > <i>Bollocherd, Bollochurde, Bullokhirde</i>	pigge~takere
gras-man > <i>gresman</i>	*bullok-man > <i>Bullokman</i>	swōn~herde
hors-man <i>Horsman, Horseman, Horsmon, Horsemon, horseman</i>	*burgh~hērde > <i>Borwherd</i>	tēchere (techour)
hōstīlēr (hostler) > <i>Hostiler, Osteler, Ostler, Osteyler, Ostiller, Oystler, Hostler, Hosteler, Husteler, Hostiller, hostelere, Osteler, hostyller, Hostelere, hosteler, Hostyler, hostillare</i>	*calf~hērde > <i>Calfherd, Kalfhirde, Calfhirde, Calvehird, Calvehirde, Calfhurd, Calverde, Calfhird, Calferde, Calverd</i>	
kēpere > <i>Kepere</i>	*calf (calve, calves, calvere)~knave > <i>Kalveknave, Calueknave, Calveknave, Caluerknave, Caluesknave, Calverknave</i>	
lēdere > <i>ledere, leeder</i>	*currier > <i>conreor, Curur, Coureer, Conreur, couraour, Coureour, Currayour, Cunreyour, corayour, Curreyour, Curreour, Curreior, corear, Curier</i>	
lōkere > <i>Loker, Lokar, Lokere, Lokar, Louker</i>	*daie-man > <i>Deyman</i>	
marshal > <i>Marescal, Maskercal, Marescald, Mascherell, mareschall, Maskerel, Marshal, Mareschall, Marscal, Mareschale, Mareschal, Marechal, Marschal, marchal, Marchale, mareschal, Marchall, marsshall</i>	*drencher > <i>Drencher</i>	
	*eue~hērde > <i>Yowehirde, Ewehurde, Yewhird, Ewehird, Yowarde, Owherde</i>	
	*fee~master > <i>Feemaister</i>	
	*ferrer > <i>Ferrur, Ferur, Farrour</i>	
	*float-man > <i>Floteman</i>	
	*fōder > <i>Fodere, Fodere, Fodier</i>	
	*folder > <i>faulder</i>	
	*fore~ward > <i>Forward, Foreward, Forewardes</i>	
	*galter > <i>Galter</i>	
	*gelde~hērde > <i>Geldehyrd, Geildehirde, Geldehirde, Geldhurd</i>	
	*gōs-man > <i>Gosman, Goceman</i>	
	*gōs~swein > <i>Goswayn</i>	
	*gōt~carl > <i>Gotenecherl</i>	
	*gōter (gater) > <i>Gatier, Geytere, Gater, Goter, Gotere</i>	
	*gōt~grōm > <i>Gotegrom</i>	
	*gōt~hērde > <i>Gothirde, Gateherde, Gotehird, Gaythirde, Gaytehird, Gaythurd, Gateherde, Gotherde, Gayterd</i>	
	*gōt-man > <i>Gateman, Gaytman, Gooteman, Goteman</i>	
	*grāsier > <i>Grasier, Grasiere, Garsere, Grasyer, grasier</i>	

Settled usage	Unsettled usage	Limited usage
milkere > <i>Melkere, Milker, Milkar, Melkare, Melker</i>	*grēser > <i>Greser</i>	
mukker > <i>Mukere, Muker, Moker, Moukor</i>	*hacchere > <i>hachur, Hetchere, Haccher, Hecchere, hatcher</i>	
nēt-drīvere > <i>Netdriver</i>	*hen (henne)-man > <i>Henneman, Henman, Heneman</i>	
nēt-hērde > <i>Nethirde, Netebird, Nethird</i>	*hērder > <i>Herder, Herdere, Hurder</i>	
nōut-hērde > <i>noutebird, Nouthirde, Nauthird, Nautherde, Noutehirde, nouthird, Noutherd</i>	*herds-man > <i>Herdeman</i>	
oxe-hērde > <i>Oxhirde, Oxhird, Oxehird, Oxherd, Ocsehurde</i>	*hog(ge-hālier) > <i>hoghalere</i>	
pāģe > <i>Page, page</i>	*hog(ge-man) > <i>Hoggeman, Hogeman</i>	
palefrei-man > <i>Palfreyman, Palfayman, Palfraimon, Palfreman, Paleframon, Pallefrayman, Palframan</i>	*hog(ge-rēve) > <i>Hoggreue</i>	
palefreiūur > <i>Palfreur, Palefreur, Palefreur, Palfreyur, Palefreyur, Palefrayur, Palefayur, Palefreour, palefreiour, palfreyur, Palfreyour</i>	*hors-drīvere > <i>Horsdriver</i>	
palefrei-pāģe > <i>palfraypage, Palfraypage</i>	*kide-man > <i>Kideman, Kydeman</i>	
pastorēl > <i>Pasturel</i>	*kīn-ward > <i>Kyneward</i>	
pastōur > <i>pastor, Pastur, Pastor, Pastour</i>	*lāthman > <i>Latheman</i>	
rother-hērde > <i>Rotherherde, Retherherde, Rutherherde, Rozerherd</i>	*lock-hērde > <i>Lockhert</i>	
shēp-hērde > <i>Chephird, Sepherd, Schepherde, Sephurde, Scephurde, Ssepherd, Sepherde, Sepeherd, Shepperde, Schiphird, Shipherde, Shepehird, Schephierd, Sheparde, Shepehird, Chepherde, Shiphierde, Shuphurde, Shuppurd, Schephurde, Scheipherde, Cheyphurde, Chephurd, Chephurde, Shepherd, Shephard, Scephirde, Shepharde, shepurde, Shipurde, Shippurde, Sephirde, Shephurde, Shipherd, schepurde</i>	*lock-ward > <i>Lokward, Locward</i>	
	*lōmb-hērde > <i>Lambhyrde, Lambhurde, Lambehird, Lomherde, Lambeherde, Lompharde, Lambhierd</i>	
	*lōmb-grōm > <i>Lambegrom, Lambergrom</i>	
	*med-hērde > <i>Medherd</i>	
	*milkster > <i>Milkster</i>	
	*motōner > <i>Motoner</i>	
	*motōun-man > <i>Multonman</i>	
	*muk-drauer > <i>mukdragher</i>	
	*mūle-grōm > <i>Mulegrom</i>	
	*mule-man > <i>Muleman</i>	
	*mūle-ward > <i>muleward</i>	
	*oxe-man > <i>Oxeman, Oxeman</i>	
	*pastūre-hērde > <i>Pasturherde</i>	
	*penner > <i>Penner</i>	
	*pigge-man > <i>Pigman</i>	
	*pigge-hērde > <i>Pyghurde</i>	
	*quīe-hērde > <i>Quihird, Whihird</i>	
	*rother-drīvere > <i>retherdryver</i>	
	*shēp-drīvere > <i>Schepdriuere</i>	
	*shēp-grōm > <i>Schepgrom, Schipgrom</i>	
	*shēp-man > <i>Scipman, Sipman, Schipman, Schepman, Schepman, Schapman</i>	
	*shēp-rēve > <i>schepreve, sheperefe, Shepereve</i>	
	*shēp-ward > <i>Shepeward, Shipward, Shypward</i>	
	*sōue-hālier > <i>Sowehaler, Sowehaler</i>	
	*sōue (sue)-hērde > <i>Sueherd</i>	
	*stēre-hērde > <i>Sterherd</i>	
	*stēre-lēche > <i>Styirleche</i>	
	*stirk-hērde > <i>Stirkehird, Strikhirde, Stirkerd</i>	
	*stōde-hērde > <i>Stodhyrda, Stodhurd, Stodhirde, Stodehard, Studherd, Stoderd, Stodard</i>	

Settled usage	Unsettled usage	Limited usage
shēp~hērdes (se > <i>Schepherdes, Sheperdes</i> shēre > <i>Scherher, Scherar, Scherer, Schirere, sherar, Sherare, Sherere, Sherer, Sherere</i> stābler > <i>Stabler, Establer, Stablere, Stabeler, Stabiler, Stablier, Stabelere</i> swōn > <i>Swon, Swan, Suon, Swoun, Swoon</i> wātrēr > <i>Waterer</i>	*stōde-man > <i>Stodman</i> *stot-hērde > <i>Stothard, Stothirde, Stothurd, Stotard, Stotherd</i> *teg-hērde > <i>Teghurde</i> *tūn-hērde > <i>Tunherd, Tunherd</i> *tup(pe-hērde) > <i>Tophird, Tuphird</i> *tupper > <i>Toppare, Tupper, Toppere</i> *washer > <i>Wassere, Wascere</i> *wether-hērde > <i>Wethyrhryrde, Wetherherde, Wetherhirde, Weydurherd, Wedirhed</i> *wōde-hērde > <i>Wodehirde, Wodehirde</i>	

Oksana Dobrovolska. Galvijų augintojų pavadinimai vidurinėje anglų kalboje: leksinės-teminės grupės istorinis vystymasis

Šis straipsnis skirtas vidurinės anglų kalbos (senosios anglų kalbos ir anglų-normanų kalbų mišinio) galvijų piemenų ir augintojų pavadinimų etimologinės struktūros, funkcinės diferenciacijos ir chronologinės stratifikacijos bendrajam tyrimui. Tyrimas reikšmingas todėl, kad kol kas trūksta bent kiek platesnių vidurinės anglų kalbos žodyno, ypač profesijų, kaip jo posistemės, pavadinimų studijų. Šių terminų funkcinės diferenciacijos tyrimas paremtas komunikacinio ir istorinio požiūrio principais. To laikotarpio anglų kalbos profesijų pavadinimų terminai skirstomi į dvi klases: bendriniai pavadinimai (pagal savo nominatyvinę funkciją) ir tikriniai vardai, ypač pavardės (atliekančios asmens įvardinimo funkciją kaip papildomą komponentą to asmens įvardijimo formulėje). Kiekvienoje žodyno etimologinėje grupėje leksinė medžiaga paskirstyta pagal funkcinį principą ir išskirtos trys profesinių terminų grupės: pirma, tai terminai, kurie funkcionuoja kaip bendriniai daiktavardžiai ir kaip tikriniai vardai; antra, tie, kurie funkcionuoja tik kaip tikriniai vardai asmens įvardijimo formulėse; trečia – tai tie, kurie funkcionuoja tik kaip bendriniai pavadinimai.

Tyrimu nustatyta, kad vidurinėje anglų kalboje naudoti 157 gyvulių augintojų pavadinimai, kas sudaro 6,5 % visų profesinių terminų; 90 % iš jų yra angliški žodžiai (iš jų 24 % yra skoliniai ir sulietiniai žodžiai), 10 % yra lotynų, prancūzų arba dvigubos kilmės (lotynų/ prancūzų kalbų) žodžių. Anglišių žodžių ir skolinių santykis yra 9:1.

Santrauka

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